

HadISDH.marine Update Document

Kate Willett (MOHC), 12th April 2021

General Notes:

The HadISDH.marine.1.1.0.2020f contains all 12 months of 2020. There are no major changes (X). There is a minor code change to the calculation of the actual gridded values so the Y variable has been incremented from 0 to 1. There are no historical changes, or bug fixes so the Z variable remains the same. Keep up to date with subsequent changes and analyses at <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2021/04/2021-updates.html>.

Version Number X.Y.Z.0000p/f:

1.1.0.2020f

Major Changes X:

- None

Minor Changes Y:

- Given the issues of biases in the actual values, due to uneven sampling over space and time across the gridbox month, we have modified the calculation methodology. These are now the 1981-2010 climatological value for the gridbox month (e.g., January) plus the anomaly value for the gridbox month (e.g. January 1973). Note that the gridbox anomalies are averaged from the point anomalies which were created by subtracting the pentad 1x1 degree gridbox climatological average for 1981-2010.

Bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

- None

Start Date DD.MM.YYYY: 1973-01-01

End Date DD.MM.YYYY: 2020-12-31

Hadisdh Data Format (Baseline documentation): URL: <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1477>

Reference: No change

Other notes: The HadISDH update/analyses blog is here:

<https://hadisdh.blogspot.com/2021/04/2021-updates.html>